

Building Roadmaps to Industrial
Decarbonisation and Green Economy
through EU-China Cooperation

D7.1 – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) Plan and Visual Identity

WP7 – Open & FAIR science, Mutual Learning,
Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation

<https://www.eu-china-bridge.eu>

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Lead beneficiary	HOLISTIC S.A. [HOL]		
Responsible author	Georgios Xexakis	Email	office@holisticsa.gr
	HOL	Phone	+30 210 6394 608
Contributors	Ioanna Bala [HOL], Thomi Nanasi [HOL]		
Reviewer(s)	Chun Xia [WI], Dagmar Kiyar [WI]		
Edited and submitted by	Chun Xia [WI]		
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EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the Description of the Action (DoA)

No changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable will serve as a reference document among consortium partners to support the communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities of the project.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

This report is the initial strategy for the communication, dissemination, and exploitation (CDE) of EU-CHINA BRIDGE to relevant audiences. Among other goals, the project will advance the knowledge on technology innovations for decarbonising energy intensive industries in the EU and China and co-create innovative modelling by combining cutting-edge bottom-up and integrated assessment modelling to quantify net-zero sustainable pathways. The report starts by defining the objectives of the CDE strategy and Key Performance Indicators that will be used for the project's promotion activities. The report then identifies the target audiences and stakeholder groups of the project including policymakers, scientists, private sector entities, NGOs and other organisations. Potential promotional channels and means to reach the target audiences are also presented, with highlights being the project's website, the Co-creation Workshops, the Stakeholder Dialogues, and capacity development and training events to the new model and datasets created by the project. By the time that this report was published, the main communication channels and visual identity material has been already created, including the logo, the project template, the main promotional materials (e.g., posters and flyers), the newsletter template as well as the project website and the social media accounts. In the upcoming months, CDE activities will intensify, including frequent posts to the project's social media accounts, promoting the website, sending newsletters, developing the first videos, infographics and media articles, and participating in multiple events.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This report.

History of changes

Date/Version	Status	Changes
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Preface

EU-CHINA BRIDGE will support the transition to a climate-neutral and resilient society in both Europe and China by jointly advancing knowledge on technology innovations and roadmaps for decarbonising energy intensive industries, co-creating innovative modelling by combining cutting-edge bottom-up and integrated assessment modelling to quantify net-zero sustainable pathways, and developing the most updated and comprehensive emissions data. It will intensively engage relevant stakeholders from both regions, enhancing dialogues, and fostering mutual learning among policymakers, industries, and experts. It will deliver two open-source EU-China joint technology inventories of promising net-zero emission technology options for the iron & steel and chemical industries, two co-implemented demonstrations of promising technologies in China, and co-created scale-up paths and roadmaps of the selected industrial technologies in both regions. It will also develop the most up-to-date, high-resolution, multi-sectoral, national and regional GHG and short-lived climate pollutant emission inventories as well as dynamic monitoring of key emission sources at high spatiotemporal granularity. A state-of-the-art modelling framework will be developed, exploiting and advancing cutting-edge and established modelling tools for EU and China, using the latest emissions data, representing technology and policy options, enabling assessment of socioeconomic impacts, covering multiple economic sectors and regions, and offering high spatial and technology detail. The enhanced models will be used to co-produce net-zero pathways for the EU and China, explicitly assessing co-benefits and trade-offs of climate policies with other societal goals while exploring cooperation policies and governance to drive the global transformation and assessing the distributional and global-level implications of the two regions' decarbonisation. The pathways will be documented in new workspaces in the I²AM PARIS platform.

WI – Wuppertal Institut fuer Klima, Umwelt, Energie gGmbH	DE	
E3M – E3-Modelling AE	GR	
IIASA – Internationales Institut fuer angewandte Systemanalyse	AT	
UoB – The University of Birmingham	UK	
ICCS – Institute of Communication and Computer Systems	GR	
HOL – HOLISTIC IKE	GR	
ITE – University of Kassel	DE	
THU-SA – Tsinghua University	CN	
THU-CE – Department of Chemical Engineering, Tsinghua University	CN	
THU-DESS – Department of Earth System Science, Tsinghua University	CN	
RUC – Renmin University of China	CN	
SDU – Shandong University	CN	
CHINACOAL – China National Coal Group Corporation	CN	
BITARIM – Advanced Research Institute of Multidisciplinary Sciences, Beijing Institute of Technology	CN	
FULONG – Inner Mongolia Fulong Heating Engineering Technology Co., LTD	CN	
BIT-ME – School of Mechanical Engineering, Beijing Institute of Technology	CN	

Executive Summary

EU-CHINA BRIDGE will support the transition to a climate-neutral and resilient society in both Europe and China by jointly advancing knowledge on technology innovations and roadmaps for decarbonising energy intensive industries and by co-creating innovative modelling by combining cutting-edge bottom-up and integrated assessment modelling to quantify net-zero sustainable pathways. This report describes the initial strategy for the communication, dissemination, and exploitation (CDE) of information and results of the project to relevant audiences.

The report starts by an introduction to the project and its research outputs. These outputs include two open-source EU-China joint technology inventories of promising net-zero emission technology options for the iron & steel and chemical industries, up-to-date, high-resolution, multi-sectoral, national and regional GHG and short-lived climate pollutant emission inventories and a state-of-the-art modelling framework, advancing cutting-edge and established modelling tools for EU and China. Based on these outputs, the report delineates the objectives of the CDE strategy as well as the Key Performance Indicators that are set for the project's promotion activities. The report then identifies the target audiences and stakeholder groups of the project including policymakers, scientists, private sector entities, NGOs, and other organisations. Examples of organisations are provided for each target audience based on the initial understanding of the project and will be further expanded in the future.

Potential promotional channels and means to reach the target audiences are also presented. Central to the communication and dissemination process is the project's website, providing a one-stop-shop for the users to learn about the project and find links to every promotional material and research products of the project. Other highlights of the project include stakeholder engagement activities which will take the form of in-depth Co-creation Workshops with small groups of stakeholders (~10-40 participants each) and larger Stakeholder Dialogues to discuss and validate project results (~50-80 participants each). Additionally, capacity development and training events will be organised to promote data sharing and model co-development between the two regions and provide hand-on training on the use of models, datasets, technology roadmaps and other outcomes of the project.

External communication channels are also envisioned to play an instrumental role to the project's CDE, including social media accounts in X, LinkedIn, and BlueSky. Other channels include promotion activities to partner websites and events such as conferences and workshops and synergies with other relevant projects. A tailor-made visual identity package for the project has been already developed. This visual identity is used already in the design of the project website and will be used throughout the project for promotional materials including articles, infographics, videos, posters, and presentations. In the upcoming months, CDE activities will intensify, including posting frequently to social media, promoting the website, sending newsletters, developing the first videos, infographics and media articles, and participating in multiple events.

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1 Introduction

EU-CHINA BRIDGE will support the transition to a climate-neutral and resilient society in both Europe and China by jointly advancing knowledge on technology innovations and roadmaps for decarbonising energy intensive industries, co-creating innovative modelling by combining cutting-edge bottom-up and integrated assessment modelling to quantify net-zero sustainable pathways, and developing the most updated and comprehensive emissions data. In order to achieve these goals, the project will intensively engage relevant stakeholders from both regions, enhancing dialogues, and fostering mutual learning among policymakers, industries, and experts.

Overall, the project will deliver:

- two open-source EU-China joint technology and policy inventories of promising net-zero emission technology options for the iron & steel and chemical industries;
- two co-implemented demonstrations of promising technologies in China;
- co-created scale-up paths and roadmaps of the selected industrial technologies in both regions;
- up-to-date, high-resolution, multi-sectoral, national and regional GHG and short-lived climate pollutant emission inventories;
- a state-of-the-art modelling framework, advancing cutting-edge and established modelling tools for EU and China, using the latest emissions inventories;
- co-produced net-zero pathways for the EU and China using the new modelling framework.

Towards these efforts, it will be key to establish and maintain regular interactions with stakeholders and interested parties to ensure the successful co-creation, dissemination, and exploitation of project results. This report describes the initial strategy for the communication, dissemination, and exploitation (CDE) of information and results of the project to relevant audiences. Overall, the CDE plan has the following objectives:

1. communicating project results and successful practices to demonstrate the project's impact to a wider audience in EU and China;
2. creating the means to disseminate results to stakeholders, including policymakers, industries, and the scientific community, motivating them to exploit project results;
3. promoting the exploitation potential of the project's flagship outputs, both during and beyond the project life.

These objectives, along with other special requirements for the project, are described in detail in Chapter 2. In order to fulfil these objectives, the CDE plan also discusses the target audiences and their characteristics and outlines communication channels to share project results so that they are openly available and easily accessible to everyone. Additionally, the plan describes a list of methods tailored to each target group, such as communication materials for the general public, policy briefs for policymakers, as well as external conferences and synergies and collaborations with other EU projects for academic dissemination.

In summary, the CDE plan is structured based on the following questions on the promotion process:

- **To whom?** Identification of the audiences to which the project will be promoted (Chapter 3).
- **How?** Analysis of potential promotional channels and selection of the most appropriate ones,

according to the target audience and the message to be disseminated (Chapter 4).

- **What?** Planning and implementation of the CDE activities (Chapter 5 for the initial communication materials and Chapter 6 for next steps on improving promotion efforts).

2 Goals and targets of the CDE plan

2.1 The three pillars of promotion: Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation

Communication is the process of informing the widest possible audience, including the media and the wider public, regarding the project and its results. EU-CHINA BRIDGE will be mainly communicated as a joint effort between researchers from the EU and China, focused on jointly developing advanced technology roadmaps and conducting in-depth analyses of policies and governance related to industrial decarbonization in both regions, overall net-zero strategies, and the most up-to-date greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions data. This collaborative aspect comes at a key time where regional rivalries monopolise the news, such as the recently announced EU tariffs on imports of electric vehicles from China. Thus, the main communication message of EU-CHINA BRIDGE would be that collaborations between the research communities of EU and China can be successful and can lead to benefits and solutions for the transition of both regions. We will also emphasise the need for decarbonisation pathways with a more inter-regional perspective, especially in the industrial decarbonisation that is strongly interrelated to global trade and supply chains.

Dissemination is the process of transferring produced knowledge and results to enable others to use and exploit them. Dissemination focuses on the results of the initiative, rather than the initiative itself, as well on how the outcomes can be exploited by interested parties. The main audiences suitable for dissemination are the ones who could use the results in their operation. Policymakers from China and the EU (from both national and regional levels) will be a natural target audience for project outcomes such as the modelled net-zero pathways and technology roadmaps. Industrial decision-makers would be also interested in the scaling-up paths, technology roadmaps, and pathways and in their impacts on and requirements from industry. Modelling researchers and social scientists will also be an important audience, as the project will aim to strengthen the dialogue between Chinese and European experts, improve the quality and accuracy of their models, enhance the integration of SSH into modelling, through mutual learning and exchange. Lastly, NGOs and international climate and sustainable development organisations will be interested in the industrial technology roadmaps and EU and China net-zero pathways due to common interests.

Exploitation is the effective practical use of project results through scientific, economic, political, or societal routes of utilisation. The objective of exploitation is to go one step further than dissemination and turn research and innovation actions into concrete value and impact for society. Thus, the main audiences of exploitation are the same as the ones suitable for dissemination. Examples of successful exploitation activities would include policymakers using project findings to inform their climate strategies and industrial decarbonisation policies and industrial actors using the technology roadmaps to inform their strategic planning.

2.2 Overall Targets

Creating a living document

The CDE plan will be periodically updated throughout the project and specifically on Month 18 and 36. Apart from this report, we will continuously monitor all CDE activities through an online CDE tracker¹ where each

¹ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1y-9pA2Hzpix2tgWBcc6We3DMLg6-AZD6/edit?usp=sharing&ouid=100626678533933877508&rtpof=true&sd=true>

consortium member can add events organised by the project, external events where project partners represent the project, and social media posts on the project's account. The CDE tracker would also track useful metrics such as the views of the posts and the number of participants in the events. A similar tracker would also monitor the development, publication, and dissemination of scientific articles, deliverables, policy briefs, and other written outputs of the project².

Customising information to target audiences

The CDE strategy will take into account a customised approach to successfully communicate the project's key messages to its various target groups based on the audience segmentation that is initially selected (see Chapter 3). Accordingly, the WP7 team will create distinct core messages for each group and link them with appropriate communication channels. Each target audience has formal and informal channels for communication (e.g., scientific publications versus scientific groups in X and LinkedIn). Therefore, in addition to being mindful of the language used, it is important to consider communication style and tone. While the essential scientific content will stay unchanged, communication initiatives will be adapted for the various stakeholder groups and communication channels.

Adopting an inclusive and gender-sensitive approach

The CDE team will strive to reach good balance of stakeholders of different genders, ages, and backgrounds in its communication and dissemination activities. Gender will be a focal point in EU-CHINA BRIDGE and will be factored in the modelling activities of the project by, e.g., analysing gender implications of pathways to net zero. The gender dimension will be also considered in the policy analysis of industrial waste heat utilisation (IWHU) for district heating. Furthermore, gender will be further emphasised in Co-Creation Workshops (WP1) and Stakeholder Dialogues (WP7). We will ensure that stakeholder representation in these events is gender-balanced and strive to achieve a gender balance with at least 50% representation of women in stakeholder groups, which will be considered as a part of the design, planning and organisation of these events (e.g., attendance at events, keynote addresses, setting agendas, etc.).

Planning for a travelling restriction-resilient CDE

Due to uncertainties related to major global disturbances such as an eventual resurgence of COVID-19 or another pandemic, appropriate methodological alternatives have been identified to ensure that the co-creation, dissemination, and communication activities can continue. While online meetings and communication have become common during the last years, for the sake of building trust with the project team and with external stakeholders, physical events will still be used when possible. In cooperation with the project coordinator, the CDE team will constantly monitor major global disturbances and decide when each methodological alternative will be used. Table 1 shows activities that are identified as potentially vulnerable to such disturbances, along with their methodological alternatives.

²<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1GiTyMg6mNqRemy3aYwLJKxyB7K2o8xB/edit?usp=sharing&oid=100626678533933877508&rtpof=true&sd=true>

Table 1. Project activities that can be potentially affected by travelling restrictions

Activity	Preferred implementation	Methodological alternatives
Co-creation Workshops, Stakeholder Dialogues, Capacity building and training events	In-person and virtual workshops	Only virtual workshops, carefully designed to reduce video-call fatigue and secure time for discussion and input from all participants
Annual project meetings among consortium partners	In-person meetings (hybrid)	Online meetings through Microsoft Teams, Zoom, or Google Meet)
Conferences, pitch meetings with policymakers, and other communication and dissemination activities	In-person and online activities	Only online through Microsoft Teams, Zoom, or Google Meet

Supporting open access

Unless they are marked as confidential, all deliverables will be uploaded in the project website and Zenodo with a Creative Commons open-access license³. Similarly, we will also strive to make new model code available in GitHub using open-source licensing. Regarding scientific publications, we will prioritise not only high-impact but also fully open-access journals offering, when feasible, open peer review, such as Open Research Europe which will be considered as a possible outlet. In the case of hybrid or transformative journals, the gold open access option will be selected, and the APC will be immediately covered via institutional agreements of participating organisations. Access to supporting datasets will be made immediately available in a dedicated Zenodo community⁴, using Creative Commons licenses for reusability and DOIs for findability.

Going paper-free

The CDE strategy is designed to be as paper-free as possible. Printed material will be used sparingly and only when deemed necessary to the CDE activity at hand such as on physical events. However, visual identity templates and communication materials will be provided openly on the website (see Chapter 5), allowing any interested party to download and use them.

2.3 Monitored CDE activities and indicators

To ensure that project results are successfully communicated and disseminated, a set of key performance indicators (KPIs) have been set and presented in Tables 2 and 3, along with expected audiences and monitoring

³ This mandate concerns European partners; partners in China shall consider releasing code as open source but are not mandated by their funding agency.

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/communities/eu-china-bridge>

tools. Progress towards these targets will be monitored on a regular basis, to confirm that the project is on track to achieve them or to take corrective measures if necessary. The communication channels and materials to achieve these targets are detailed in Chapters 4 and 5 respectively.

Table 2. Communication activities

Activity	Objective	Expected audience and KPIs	Monitoring tool
Visual identity	Create visually compelling material for stakeholders in the EU and China	All stakeholder groups: policy, industry, research, civil society	All materials will be published on the project website
Project website	Present the project, disseminate its outcomes, and serve as an online library of all project publications	All stakeholder groups: 2000 unique visitors/year 30% of return visitors	Google Analytics
Social media	Create familiarity with the project, share results among scientists, policy, industry, citizens, and other groups	All stakeholder groups: 1,000 uses of EU-CHINA BRIDGE hashtag or handle, 500 followers on LinkedIn/Twitter 1000 on WeChat	Analytics of social media platforms
Newsletters (four per year)	Involve stakeholders in the progress of the project; share news, commentaries, and project outcomes	All stakeholder groups: 3000 recipients/downloads 30% opening rate	Email monitoring system; Website download analytics
Infographics & videos	Explain pertinent concepts and outcomes of the project	Industry, society, policymakers: >1,000 views/downloads	YouTube/Instagram stats; # downloads
Media articles	Explain major outcomes of the project via non-technical language.	Civil society: At least 5 articles	Links of articles shared on website

Table 3. Dissemination activities

Activity	Objective	Expected audience and KPIs	Monitoring tool
Enhanced I ² AM PARIS platform	Facilitating harmonisation /modelling; fostering co-creation; validating modelling results	All stakeholder groups: 2000 unique users/year 30% of return visitors	Google Analytics
Policy briefs	Inform EU and Chinese policymakers and industry decision-makers	Policymakers, industry: 12 policy briefs	Number of briefs

Scientific outreach	Disseminate project results in academic outlets	Academia: > 15 papers; > 6 conferences	Digital monitoring, OpenAIRE entries
Networking activities with relevant EU and Chinese projects	Share results among different research communities and create synergies with projects under similar topics	Academia: Project referenced in 10 projects (websites, reports, etc.), joint papers and project meetings	Digital monitoring, # of joint papers & acknowledged projects in papers

Additionally, several project tasks are directly related to dissemination and exploitation objectives of the project such as the co-creation work of WP₁ and the capacity building events of Task 7.5 of WP₇. Table 4 presents all such tasks that were identified at the project's inception stage. While the CDE project team (mainly including members of HOLISTIC) is not directly involved in most of these tasks, it will nevertheless support project partners in these activities as they see fit, e.g., promoting the capacity development workshops etc. Further relevant tasks may be added in the table as the project is evolving.

Table 4. WPs and tasks that are directly related to dissemination and exploitation objectives

WP/Tasks	Dissemination & exploitation objectives	Activities	Month
WP₁	Fostering direct productive co-creation workshops with stakeholders	Mapping stakeholders; interviews in-person & online workshops	1-30
WPs 3, 4, 6	Ensuring comprehensibility of the results, tailoring them to the needs of policymakers and industrial stakeholders	Discussing results with stakeholders, Drafting of Policy briefs	8-34
Task 7.2	Reaching out a broader audience of stakeholders and experts; Inform policymakers and industrial, and other stakeholders on the project findings and promote their exploitation	Stakeholder dialogues at multiple levels (with the EU and China, between the EU and China, international)	9-36
Tasks 7.4, 7.6	Expansion of the I ² AM PARIS platform, establishing it as a vessel of the EU and international modelling community	Enhanced I ² AM PARIS platform: updated model information, workspaces, insights, diagnostics, protocols; open science principles; FAIR data	7-36
Task 7.5	Building capacity of model and data researchers in the EU and China and globally	Training workshops for researchers EU, China, and globally, online workshops, open-source data and modelling tools	6-36
WP₂₋₆	Engaging with the wider academic community	Open access online dataset, papers to	6-36

		scientific journals, individual conference contributions, concerted conference sessions	
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3 Target audiences

For implementing successful and impactful CDE activities, it is crucial to have a thorough awareness of the interests and motivations of the stakeholders that are considered as target audiences for the project. As EU-CHINA BRIDGE aims to engage with diverse audiences in the EU and China, the CDE team will aim to understand the characteristics of potentially interested parties, facilitate tailored communication, and implement different engagement strategies for each audience. Since most of the members of the CDE team are coming from the EU, it will be essential to closely cooperate with the Chinese partners and participate in engagement events with Chinese stakeholders in order to understand the context and relevant audiences for that region. Table 5 shows the target audiences that have been identified at the project's inception, along with relevant communication methods for each audience.

Table 5. Target audiences and relevant communication/dissemination methods

Target audiences	Examples of stakeholders	Relevant methods
Scientists, Researchers, Academia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Modelers working with integrated assessment models and climate-economy models in general Researchers working on climate change mitigation topics Industrial ecology scientists Researchers on international governance and collaboration topics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific publications and project deliverables Scientific conferences (e.g., international conferences such as IAMC, EU conferences such as ECEMP, and other relevant modelling-relevant events in China) Social media posts Infographics and videos (shared via website and YouTube) Co-creation workshops and Stakeholder Dialogues Capacity building and training events I²AM PARIS platform
Horizon Europe projects, European, Chinese, and international modelling consortia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrated Assessment Modelling Consortium European Climate and Energy Modelling Forum H2020 PARIS REINFORCE H2020 NDC ASPECTS HEU IAM COMPACT HEU DIAMOND 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participation in project clustering events Participation in modelling conferences and meetings Mailing lists and newsletters Co-creation workshops and Stakeholder Dialogues I²AM PARIS platform
Policymakers at all scales	European Commission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policy briefs Policy-relevant conferences and events (e.g.,

	<p>European Parliament National EU governments Chinese government officials EU-China flagship initiative on Climate Change and Biodiversity</p>	<p>COP meetings, EU Sustainable Energy Week, EU Green Week) Co-creation workshops and Stakeholder Dialogues I²AM PARIS platform</p>
<p>Industry decision-makers</p>	<p>World steel association CEFIC IEA Thyssenkrupp COVESTRO BASF China Energy Reserve and Chemicals Group Company China Energy Investment World Business Council for Sustainable Development</p>	<p>Industry-relevant events Social media posts in LinkedIn Infographics and videos (shared via website and YouTube) Co-creation workshops and Stakeholder Dialogues Policy briefs I²AM PARIS platform</p>
<p>Civil society and NGOs</p>	<p>Steel and chemical associations in the EU, China, and globally WWF, Greenpeace, WRI, GIZ</p>	<p>Social media posts News articles Infographics and videos (shared via website and YouTube) Co-creation workshops and Stakeholder Dialogues</p>
<p>Media</p>	<p>The Conversation The Manufacturer South China Morning Post RENEW Industry EURACTIV Carbon Brief Climatechangemitigation.eu ClimateChangePost Dialogue Earth</p>	<p>Press releases News articles</p>

Based on the experience of the WP7 team with previous Horizon projects relating to energy and climate

modelling (e.g., H2020 PARIS REINFORCE, H2020 NDC ASPECTS, HEU IAM COMPACT, HEU DIAMOND), an initial list of stakeholders has been identified for each of the target audience categories. Examples of these stakeholders can be seen in Table 5, while for media outlets a more complete list can be found on the project's Google Drive⁵. Stakeholder lists will be further enhanced through relevant contacts of all project partners, newsletter subscribers, and invitees in engagement events. In line with the rules of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), exchanging sensitive information about the stakeholders between partner organisations in the consortium will be avoided, unless explicit consent is provided by a stakeholder. Each partner organisation will be in charge of establishing and maintaining contact with their own stakeholders, under the coordination of the CDE team.

⁵https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1iaLRs4s3dRBw9iVYuYR69QfPTV1s_zn/edit?usp=share_link&ouid=100626678533933877508&rtpof=true&sd=true

4 Promotional channels

At the heart of the CDE plan is the design and implementation of promotional channels to reach target audiences, disseminate messages and outputs, and ensure their exploitation. The promotional channels are the routes through which the messages from the project find their relevant audiences, including the project website and the I²AM PARIS platform, posts on social media, participation in conferences and others. These channels are then used to distribute communication means that encapsulate messages from the project, i.e., publications, infographics, or videos.

Each combination of promotional channels and means has a particular function and level of promotion. For instance, a scientific publication contains technical details that aim to provide scientists, modellers, and researchers with a more in-depth view of the project's outcome. On the other hand, an infographic is better suited to showcase the project's concept and results to a broader audience, whereas a policy brief is providing actionable and policy-relevant findings from the project to decision makers.

4.1 Project website

The project website is online and can be publicly accessed at <https://eu-china-bridge.eu>. It will serve as an one-stop-shop for EU-CHINA BRIDGE, providing comprehensive information about the project and the consortium team, news and updates, as well as links to all project outputs including deliverables, publications, and conference slides. In addition, the website will be continuously updated throughout the project's duration and will stay online at least two years after the end of the project.

The website is designed in line with the project's colour palette, logo, and the overall visual identity and has been developed using the open-source Drupal framework (version 10). Apart from being open source, Drupal was selected as it offers a powerful Content Management System (CMS), packing many features and extensions that can improve the website's responsiveness to a wide range of devices (mobiles, laptops, desktops), its security, and its accessibility to a wide variety of audiences. The website is currently provided in English but will be eventually also translated in Chinese. A reference to the I²AM PARIS⁶ platform will be also added, linking the website with the modelling documentation and result workspaces that will be developed for EU-CHINA BRIDGE. The news and material updated on the website will also serve as a content for a bilingual newsletter sent to interested stakeholders at least four times per year.

In terms of evaluating its performance, we aim to have more than 2,000 unique visitors per year, with 30% of them being return visitors. These indicators will be measured through the project's Google Analytics account which is already set up and connected to the project website. Aiming to increase its visibility, the website will be continuously promoted through the other communication and dissemination channels of the project such as social media and newsletters. The website will be maintained during the project's duration, while all updates will be installed to ensure the website's security and performance. Figure 1 showcases the homepage of the website while Figure 2 shows the website section on objectives.

⁶ <https://izam-paris.eu>

Figure 1. Homepage of the project website (upper part)

Figure 2. Section of project objectives on the website

4.2 The I²AM PARIS platform

EU-CHINA BRIDGE will provide new content and functionalities to the I²AM PARIS platform⁷, an open-access, data exchange platform for climate-economy modelling. This platform was developed, validated, and used in PARIS REINFORCE (coordinated by ICCS-NTUA), enhanced in H2020 NDC ASPECTS (coordinated by WI), as well as further expanded currently in a series of Horizon Europe projects, such as IAM COMPACT and DIAMOND (both coordinated by ICCS-NTUA).

The EU-CHINA BRIDGE website will be cross-linked to the I²AM PARIS platform, where all project models and modelling capabilities will be documented and dynamically presented, providing stakeholders with access to digestible information on each model and an overview of what they can and cannot do. It will thus allow stakeholders to understand assumptions and scenario elements (Task 6.1) and understand how different factors influence transitions and the interactions between the EU and Chinese pathways to climate neutrality (Task 6.4), essentially underpinning our co-creation activities (WP1). The platform will also provide interactive visualisations to scenario modelling results (Tasks 6.2-6.3) using different kinds of workspaces for expert and non-expert audiences. For instance, we will use a policy dashboard functionality that is available in the I²AM PARIS platform, using policy questions to structure project results and make them more relevant.

The platform will also serve as a collection of all data products produced during the project, including links to repositories of new model code (WP5), to complete datasets of scenario results (WP6), to newly developed emissions inventories (WP2), and to technology inventories and roadmaps (WP3). These products will be accompanied with documents such as deliverables, scientific publications, and technical documents to provide detailed insights into our modelling capacities, applications, key assumptions, and limitations.

4.3 Social media

Social media are online forums and platforms to exchange/share thoughts, opinions, knowledge, and expertise with a large audience and can be also used to host marketing, advertising efforts, and promotional campaigns. Apart from the website, social media channels will be key for both the communication and dissemination of the project. Overall, we have created dedicated EU-CHINA BRIDGE accounts on X⁸ (formerly known as Twitter), LinkedIn⁹, and BlueSky¹⁰ (see Figure 3 for an example). Each of these accounts will serve a different purpose: X and BlueSky will be used for communication to the general public and stakeholders from the scientific and policy communities, the LinkedIn account will target more business and industrial stakeholders. Links for all channels are also provided on a concise webpage hosted by Linktree, as shown in Figure 4. The Linktree webpage is also accessible by a QR code (also shown in Figure 4) that is placed in all visual materials of the project in order to provide to their readers fast access to all social media channels at once.

⁷ <https://izam-paris.eu>

⁸ https://x.com/eu_china_bridge

⁹ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eu-china-bridge>

¹⁰ <https://bsky.app/profile/eu-china-bridge.bsky.social>

Figure 3. Screenshot of the project account on X

Figure 4. List of all social media channels, website, and platforms of the project on Linktree

While in the project’s Grant Agreement we have suggested to create an account in Mastodon, from our recent experience with the communication of similar research projects (e.g., H2o2o NDC ASPECTS), we have concluded that this channel is not as effective as we have initially believed when we were writing the proposal for EU-CHINA BRIDGE. In contrast, BlueSky is considered much more effective in scientific communication in

our field as many members of relevant scientific groups of Twitter (e.g., #energytwitter) have started using this platform. In terms of WeChat, we will refrain from creating a new dedicated account for EU-CHINA BRIDGE based on the suggestion of our Chinese partners. Instead, we will forward news and materials to our partners to publish in their own personal and institutional WeChat accounts, ensuring thus a receptive and relevant audience from the onset of our communication.

Currently, our social media account only has some initial posts on our kick-off meeting and the start of the project. For this reason, follower numbers are currently very low. We will soon start posting at least once a week about the project or relevant topics such as on EU-China collaborations on energy and climate. Our aim will be to reach 1,000 uses of the #EU_China_Bridge hashtag or the project account handle and gain 500 followers on LinkedIn and X.

4.4 News websites and blogs

The following section presents a list of high-calibre media websites that can be contacted to communicate and disseminate project outputs to a wide audience. The list is indicative and non-exhaustive and will be modified or extended whenever necessary. It is also noted that these outlets are mostly relevant for EU stakeholders; more China-relevant outlets will be added in the future in coordination with the Chinese partners.

The Conversation

The Conversation¹¹ is an independent source of news, analysis, and expert opinion, written by academics and researchers and delivered directly to the public. It is estimated that its global audience is about 14.1 million readers per month. It is envisaged that project results can be promoted via The Conversation to audiences appropriate for dissemination and exploitation.

EURACTIV

EURACTIV¹² is an independent pan-European media network specialised in EU policymaking, covering policy processes upstream of decisions. It provides free and localised news about EU policy in twelve languages, and together with its media partners reaches 1.7 million users across Europe and the rest of the world.

The Guardian

The Guardian¹³ is an acknowledged British daily newspaper founded in 1821 reaching a total of 24.9 million people each month. It features a section dedicated to the environment, with subtopics on climate change, wildlife, energy, and pollution. It is envisaged that the project's outcomes can be promoted via The Guardian to a wide variety of audiences fulfilling all three pillars of promotion.

South China Morning Post

The South China Morning Post¹⁴ is a leading news media company that has reported on China and Asia for more than a century with global impact. Similar to The Guardian, flagship project results can be potentially promoted through this news website to achieve a very wide coverage.

¹¹ <https://theconversation.com/>

¹² <https://www.euractiv.com/>

¹³ <https://www.theguardian.com/>

¹⁴ <https://www.scmp.com>

ClimateChangePost

ClimateChangePost¹⁵ features the latest news on climate change and adaptation with a special focus on Europe. Many of its articles present the latest results from scientific publications and reports, making it an ideal conduit for the project to reach a wide range of its target audiences.

ClimateChangeNews.com

An international platform¹⁶ that covers climate change news, analysis, commentary, video, and podcasts focused on developments in global climate politics.

Euronews – Climate Now

For dissemination to a very wide audience, the Climate Now¹⁷ programme of the Euronews channel may be a good fit for the project.

Energypost.eu

Energy Post¹⁸ provides an open platform to exchange and debate energy topics for policymakers, market players, analysts, and other stakeholders and could be used to reach specialised audiences for project results.

Research*eu

Research*eu Results magazine¹⁹ covers topics of research interest in the EU. Through this magazine, results of the project can be communicated and disseminated to scientists, policymakers in the EU and Member States, and the general public.

Dialogue Earth

Dialogue Earth is an independent non-profit dedicated to producing exceptional environmental journalism and informed conversations on urgent climate and sustainability topics. They are committed to accurately portraying China's development impacts across the Global South through geopolitically even-handed reporting and constructive dialogue

4.5 Online collaboration and sharing platforms

Climatechangemitigation.eu

Climatechangemitigation.eu is a portal that collects and disseminates information from different EU-funded research projects on climate change mitigation. The project will use the portal²⁰ to promote its results to scientific and policymaking communities in the EU working on mitigation topics.

Capacity4Dev

Capacity4Dev²¹ is the European Commission's knowledge-sharing platform for development cooperation

¹⁵ <https://www.climatechangepost.com/>

¹⁶ <https://climatechangenews.com/>

¹⁷ <https://www.euronews.com/green/green-series/climate-now>

¹⁸ <http://energypost.eu/>

¹⁹ https://cordis.europa.eu/research-eu/home_en.html

²⁰ <http://climatechangemitigation.eu/>

²¹ <https://europa.eu/capacity4dev/>

aiming to improve capacity building. The platform has over 25,000 members who share, learn, and collaborate on the fields of sustainable development. This channel is ideal for dissemination and exploitation purposes since its members are scientists, industrialists, EU staff, sustainable development professionals in the EU, policymakers at the EU and global level, as well as members of civil society.

IISD SDG Knowledge Hub

The SDG Knowledge Hub²² is an online resource centre for news and commentary regarding the implementation of the United Nations' 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, including discussions on progress across all 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). It is envisaged that our outcomes can be promoted via the IISD SDG Knowledge Hub to actors involved in sustainable development, such as policymakers, scientists, NGOs, industrialists, and civil society.

4.6 Data repositories and platforms

Zenodo

Zenodo is a platform developed by CERN with the goal to provide an easy-access data repository for scientific data from all over the world and from every discipline. The project's Zenodo community²³ will form a central hub for providing open and unrestricted access to the project's publications and data, serving as a repository of all project's outputs to ensure the sustainability of project work even after the website will be suspended (two years after the end of the project).

GitHub

GitHub²⁴ is a platform for hosting open-source code, allowing extensive functionalities for version control and collaboration. GitHub will be mostly used to host the code for new model functionalities that will be developed as part of EU-CHINA BRIDGE, as well as scripts and inputs that will be used in the project's modelling exercises.

OpenAIRE

OpenAIRE²⁵ is a science-related portal, the mission of which is to provide unlimited, barrier-free, open access to research outputs financed by public funding in Europe. The use of OpenAIRE will enable the project, on one hand, to report more effectively and efficiently the outcomes of the action and, on the other, to reach a wide community of scientists, policymakers, and stakeholders interested in EU-funded research in general.

European Open Science Cloud

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)²⁶ aspires to provide European researchers, innovators, companies, and citizens with an open multi-disciplinary environment where they can publish, find and re-use data, tools and services for research, innovation, and educational purposes.

²² <http://sdg.iisd.org/>

²³ <https://zenodo.org/communities/eu-china-bridge/>

²⁴ <https://github.com/>

²⁵ <https://www.openaire.eu/>

²⁶ <https://eosc-portal.eu/>

4.7 Partners' websites/blogs

Most consortium partners have websites featuring news on their research activities. On these websites, articles on the progress of EU-CHINA BRIDGE and announcements on recent reports or upcoming events can be published. Partner websites that could be used in the future for dissemination and communication include the websites of WI²⁷, E3M²⁸, IIASA²⁹, UoB³⁰, ICCS³¹, HOL³², ITE³³, THU-SA³⁴, THU-CE³⁵, THU-DESS³⁶, RUC³⁷, SDU³⁸, CHINACOAL³⁹, BITARIM⁴⁰, FULONG⁴¹, and BIT-ME⁴². Project activities could also be promoted through partners' social media accounts and newsletters. The CDE team will keep consortium partners informed about project updates and encourage them to forward and promote these updates to their communication departments.

4.8 Peer-to-peer mailing lists

Peer-to-peer (P2P) mailing lists are subscription-based email services that enable individuals interested in specific topics to communicate with each other and exchange opinions and project results. P2P lists related to project-related topics such as energy, IAMs, and climate change mitigation can help reach audiences from academia, policymaking, and business since most subscribers are actively working in sectors affected by these topics. Examples of these lists include the lists hosted by the International Institute for Sustainable Development⁴³. These lists will be used to disseminate the project's progress and output (newsletters, press releases, and general announcements) and invite subscribers to participate in the project's co-creation events. Additionally, these mailing lists will be used to follow research and novelties from project-relevant fields.

4.9 Co-creation Workshops and Stakeholder Dialogues

Stakeholder engagement will form the backbone of all project activities and will take the form of in-depth Co-creation Workshops (WP1) with small groups of stakeholders (~10-40 participants each) and larger Stakeholder Dialogues (Task 7.2) to discuss and validate project results (~50-80 participants each). Potential audiences will be government officials and other policymakers from the EU and China, industrial representatives and associations (e.g., the World steel association, CEFIC), and international organisations (e.g., IEA, Energy

²⁷ <http://www.wupperinst.org/>

²⁸ <http://www.e3modelling.com>

²⁹ <https://iiasa.ac.at/>

³⁰ <https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/index.aspx>

³¹ <https://www.iccs.gr/en/institute-of-communication-and-computer-systems/>

³² www.holisticsa.gr

³³ <https://www.uni-kassel.de/uni/en/>

³⁴ <https://www.tsinghua.edu.cn/en/>

³⁵ <https://www.chemeng.tsinghua.edu.cn/>

³⁶ <https://www.dess.tsinghua.edu.cn/en/>

³⁷ <https://www.ruc.edu.cn/>

³⁸ <https://en.sdu.edu.cn/>

³⁹ <https://en.chinacoal.com/>

⁴⁰ <https://arims.bit.edu.cn/>

⁴¹ http://www.mglip.com/en/introduction_lab_en.html

⁴² <https://me-english.bit.edu.cn/>

⁴³ <https://enb.iisd.org/email/>

Foundation China). Consortium partners are also linked to the EU-China flagship initiative on Climate Change and Biodiversity which will form a source of potential stakeholders. Stakeholders already expressed their strong support for the EU-CHINA BRIDGE project through Letters of Intent (Thyssenkrupp, COVESTRO, World Steel Association), informal exchange (BASF, China Energy Reserve and Chemicals Group Company, China Energy Investment,), and acting as project partners in China (China National Coal Group Corporation, Inner Mongolia Fulong Heating Engineering Technology). All stakeholder engagement activities will be fully GDPR-compliant, and participants will be invited to follow the project in social media and subscribe in our newsletter.

4.10 Capacity building and training events

In the context of Task 7.5, yearly training events will be organised to promote data sharing and model co-development between the two regions and provide hand-on training on the use of models, datasets, technology roadmaps and other outcomes of the project. The events will be promoted to members of the scientific community in both Europe and China that work on topics related to climate change mitigation, energy, industrial ecology, land use, air pollution, etc. The I²AM PARIS platform will play a pivotal role for sharing model documentation and provide interactive interfaces to access and visualise all modelling results for the decarbonisation pathways produced in the project.

4.11 Scientific conferences

EU-CHINA BRIDGE partners will participate in scientific conferences to disseminate the project results to the scientific community. Additionally, conferences will be used to monitor relevant research in climate-economy modelling, industrial ecology, and other relevant topics. The following conferences have been assessed as relevant to the project:

- Annual Meeting of the Integrated Assessment Modelling Consortium (IAMC)⁴⁴
- European Climate + Energy Modelling Platform (ECEMP)⁴⁵
- International Energy Workshop⁴⁶
- Energy Modeling Forum⁴⁷
- Sustainable Development of Energy, Water and Environment Systems (SDEWES) conference⁴⁸
- Earth System Governance annual conference⁴⁹

4.12 Policy conferences

Along the duration of EU-CHINA BRIDGE from April 2024 to March 2027, three sessions of the UNFCCC's Conference of the Parties (COP) will take place. These conferences offer great opportunities to reach out to policymakers, NGOs, industrialists, scientists, and other audiences and promote the project. In terms of

⁴⁴ <https://www.iamconsortium.org/annual-meetings/>

⁴⁵ <https://www.ecemf.eu/ecemp/european-climate-and-energy-modelling-platform/>

⁴⁶ <https://www.internationalenergyworkshop.org>

⁴⁷ <https://emf.stanford.edu>

⁴⁸ <https://www.sdewes.org/>

⁴⁹ <https://www.earthsystemgovernance.org/annual-conferences/>

European-specific conferences, the European Sustainable Development Week⁵⁰ and the European Sustainable Energy Week⁵¹ will be policy-relevant fora for presenting the project's results. The project's CDE team will be also in contact with the Chinese partners in order to add here relevant policy conferences in China.

4.13 Synergies

Synergies with relevant projects can increase the outreach potential of the project's outputs and raise awareness among a broad spectrum of stakeholders. The CDE team will contact projects of interest and co-organise synergetic activities such as participating in each other's events, developing synergetic publications, and cross-disseminating information and outputs through social media and project websites. The EU-CHINA BRIDGE website will contain a section on such synergistic activities in the near future. Indicative projects for CDE synergies that will run (fully or partly) in parallel with EU-CHINA BRIDGE include the following:

- DIAMOND (HEU): Delivering the next generation of open Integrated Assessment MOdels for Net-zero, sustainable Development⁵²
- IAM COMPACT (HEU): Expanding Integrated Assessment Modelling: Comprehensive and Comprehensible Science for Sustainable, Co-Created Climate Action⁵³
- TRANSIENCE (HEU): TRANSItioning towards an Efficient, carbon-Neutral Circular European industry⁵⁴

It is noted that these projects are mainly suggested in terms of CDE collaborations. In terms of progressing scientific knowledge in the climate-economy field, EU-CHINA BRIDGE will collaborate with the aforementioned projects as well as other ongoing projects and initiatives such as the IN₄climate and NRW initiative, Global Steel Transformation, and the Horizon Europe EU-CIP. Additionally, EU-CHINA BRIDGE will be based on previous projects such as CEADS, H2020 NDC ASPECTS, H2020 ENGAGE, and H2020 ForestNavigator.

⁵⁰ <https://esdw.eu>

⁵¹ https://sustainable-energy-week.ec.europa.eu/index_en

⁵² <https://climate-diamond.eu>

⁵³ <https://www.iam-compact.eu>

⁵⁴ <https://www.transience.eu>

5 Visual identity and communication means

From the onset of the project, we have developed a visual identity to encapsulate the main characteristics of EU-CHINA BRIDGE and effectively communicate them to all relevant stakeholders. This visual identity was then used to develop a project logo, a branding guide (including colours, fonts etc.), and tailor-made templates for Microsoft PowerPoint and Word. Furthermore, several promotional materials have been developed to communicate the scope and objectives of the project, such as posters, flyers, and an institutional presentation. More such materials will be developed in the project, along with videos and infographics, to present the results and main findings of the projects. All promotional materials and visual identity will be uploaded to the website in a respective webpage.

5.1 Visual identity and communication package

5.1.1 Logo

EU-CHINA BRIDGE mainly aims to bring together modelling experts and stakeholders from the EU and China to jointly advancing technology innovations roadmaps and decarbonisation pathways for both regions, focusing especially on energy-intensive industries. The visual identity was designed to be inclusive of all partners and audiences in both China and Europe, also considering cultural differences in terms of colours, symbols, and layout. The name of the project was the primary inspiration for the logo and the visual identity that is based on the main flag colours for the two regions, that is the blue from the EU flag and the red from the flag of the People's Republic of China. A red and blue bridge-like symbol is used to further express the connection between the two regions while a sans serif font (Geometra Rounded) is used to express clarity and transparency in this connection. Similarly, the sans serif font Corbel is used for all other project text, as it was designed specifically for clarity on the screen, even at small display sizes.

The logo that was developed and used for the project can be seen in Figure 5. Figure 6 showcases other alternatives that were created and considered along with the project consortium during the first month of the project. The rest of the visual identity shown below is based on the colours and characteristics of the logo. Further visual elements will be also developed in the future with the same visual identity such as icons and glyphs. The logo as well as other visual identity materials (i.e., Word & PowerPoint templates) have been already evaluated by the coordinators and the project consortium to ensure that it is attractive for all parties.

Figure 5. Project logo

Figure 6. Alternative logos created during the initial elaboration of the project’s visual identity

5.1.2 Templates

Throughout the duration of EU-CHINA BRIDGE, there will be a variety of documents circulated among partners, disseminated to stakeholders, published on social media, or printed and shared at events. In order to consolidate the project’s visual identity and ensure uniformity and recognisability, specific templates have been created for each Microsoft Word and for PowerPoint using the same colours and styles across all material. The Word template is showcased in the current document while an example of the PowerPoint template can be seen in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Project presentation template

5.1.3 Visual identity for social media

Social media will be an important outlet for the project’s communication efforts. Based on the visual identity above, headers have been developed for all social media accounts of the project in X (Figure 8), LinkedIn, and BlueSky. Headers for other social media (e.g., WeChat for the Chinese side) will be developed upon request. Additionally, ad-hoc visual material will be developed to accompany social media posts in the future.

Figure 8. Social media header for the project's account in X

5.1.4 Flyer

A promotional flyer has been developed giving general information and creating visibility about the project (Figure 9). It has been primarily produced in English and will be translated into Chinese in the future. As with all communication package items, the flyer will be available online on the project website and will be downloaded and printed only when needed, e.g., for events and conferences about the project.

Figure 9. Project flyer

5.1.5 Leaflet

EU-CHINA BRIDGE has also produced a promotional 3-fold leaflet featuring a short project description along with concise descriptions of the project's motivation, objectives, project partners, and contact information (Figure 10). Along with the flyer, the leaflet is intended for project promotion at conferences and other events and will be only printed when needed.

Figure 10. 3-fold leaflet with information about the project

5.1.6 Poster and roll-up banner

For further establishing the project identity in major events that EU-CHINA BRIDGE organises or participates, we have developed a project poster in A3 and A0 sizes and a roll-up poster (Figure 11). The poster can be used in online poster exhibitions or printed for physical events while the roll-up banner will be mainly reserved in high-exposure events and will be printed when needed.

Figure 11. Project poster in A3 and A0 (left) and roll-up banner (right)

5.2 Communication means

5.2.1 Newsletter

The newsletter’s goal is to periodically inform interested stakeholders about the project’s progress. A regular electronic newsletter will be issued providing information on the project at least four times per year. The newsletter will incorporate inputs from all partners on the progress and key outcomes of the project, including recent deliverables, scientific publications, event participations, infographics, videos, and other materials developed by the project. The newsletter may also include news about other research activities that are relevant to the project, such as updates from other projects with similar topics (e.g., climate-economy modelling, industrial decarbonisation) as well as news related to EU-China collaborations on climate and industrial topics.

In compliance with the GDPR, a person will be included on the newsletter mailing list only if one is informed and explicit consent has been given, while the possibility of withdrawing the consent is clearly explained. Consent will be provided either by filling out an online subscription form or by direct email in case of personal contacts. In coordination with the Chinese partners, a similar process will be used to adhere to relevant requirements from the Chinese side. The template for the EU-CHINA BRIDGE newsletter can be seen in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Project presentation template

5.2.2 Promotion to partners' institutions and press releases

Similar to the newsletter, we will be in contact with the communication departments of all consortium partners to provide them with project content that can be published on the partners' newsletters, websites, and other media channels. These materials will be primarily disseminated through press releases which would be slightly more detailed than newsletter items and provide all required information for the public to understand. In addition, these press releases will be published on the project website and will be promoted on relevant media outlets.

5.2.3 Scientific publications

Scientific publications are one of the key means of disseminating the project's results to the research community and building scientific credibility for the project's work. At least 15 scientific articles will be published in open-access, high-quality, peer-reviewed journals. Journals also offering open peer review, such as Open Research Europe, will be considered as a possible outlet. In the case of hybrid or transformative journals, the gold open access option will be selected, and the APC will be immediately covered via institutional agreements of participating organisations. Access to papers and supporting datasets will be made immediately available in a dedicated project OpenAIRE/Zenodo community, using Creative Commons licenses for reusability and DOIs for findability. Moreover, the WP7 team will use its social media channels to promote the articles.

5.2.4 Policy briefs

Apart from inviting policymakers to the co-creation events, we will promote our project results through 12 policy briefs. The policy briefs will be developed based on the work of WPs 3, 4, and 6 and will provide relevant and actionable recommendations for directly informing policy in China and the EU based on our project results, considering policy cycles and relevant opportunities (e.g., revised NECPs in 2025, updated NDCs of China and the EU, long-term strategies before 2028). The briefs will be disseminated during the Stakeholder Dialogues and promoted through the project website and social media and summarised in media articles.

5.2.5 Blog posts and media articles

Articles on selected results of the project will be published in leading media websites and blogs will be disseminated via the promotional channels identified in Section 4.1. All partners will support this process by suggesting media contacts and extending the list of interesting media targets. At least five media articles are expected to be published in the project's course.

5.2.6 Videos and infographics

The WP7 team will produce videos and infographics to create awareness with the project and promote project results, especially among policymakers, industry representatives, and other non-academic stakeholders. At least five videos and five infographics will be developed throughout the project's duration and will be promoted on the project website, social media, newsletter, and other potential outlets.

6 Next steps

By the time of publication of the first version of the CDE Plan, the basic setup of communication channels and visual identity material has been already implemented. This includes the logo, the project template, the main promotional materials (e.g., posters and flyers), the newsletter template as well as the project website and the social media. Nevertheless, the lack of communication materials has limited the interaction of stakeholders with the social media, which is understandable since the initial scientific work of the project is still ongoing. Thus, the CDE strategy for the upcoming months include the following next steps:

1. Start publishing at least once per week in social media and increase the number of social media followers.
2. Complete the last design details of the website, start adding news and materials, and promote the website to project partners and the social media.
3. Send the first issues of the EU-CHINA BRIDGE newsletter (target for two issues within 2024 and four issues within 2025).
4. Prepare a first video and infographic explaining the concept of EU-CHINA BRIDGE.
5. Explore the possibility of publishing a first media article on EU-CHINA BRIDGE, potentially based on the upcoming stakeholder meetings in China in October 2024 and the 1st modelling capacity building workshop. While the stakeholder meetings will be under closed door policy, some details would be openly accessed and thus we would be able to report them in an open article.
6. Organise the first stakeholder engagement events and participate on relevant conferences.

More steps will be considered in an ad-hoc basis throughout the next academic year in order increase progress towards the KPIs of Chapter 2. Lastly, with the support of the project coordinator (WI), the CDE team will align with the Chinese partners to further explore potential CDE activities that can be implemented in China.